

GREAT

Deliverable D4.1

Underpinning Research Framework

Work Package: WP:4.1 Underpinning Research Framework

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 31/07/2023

Actual submission date: 28/07/2023

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

Deliverable Lead: University of Bolton UoB

Author(s): Paul Hollins (pah1@Bolton.ac.uk), David Griffiths (David.Griffiths@unir.net), Barbara Kieslinger (Kieslinger@zsi.at), Katharina Koller (kkoller@zsi.at)

Point of Contact: Hendrik Drachsler

Deliverable Information

Reviewers	Hendrik Drachsler (h.drachsler@dipf.de), Barbara Kieslinger (kieslinger@zsi.at), Katharina Koller (kkoller@zsi.at)
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	<p>This deliverable provides details of the research methodologies and approaches deployed in the project. The multiple methodologies adopted can facilitate and engage fully with the complex human and technical interactions of the project.</p> <p>Integral to this is the Citizen Science methodological approach. An approach that permeates research activity undertaken in the project with the aim of democratising the scientific inquiry and outputs. The primary research instrument deployed in GREAT is the Case Study details of the instrument, validation and evaluation methods are provided.</p>
Keywords	Research, Methodology, Framework
Statement of originality	<p>This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.</p>

Document History

Version	Date	Comment (Examples)
0.1	01/05/2023	Draft 0.1 document created
0.2	15/07/2023	Main content added to all sections
0.3	17/07/2023	Peer review and detailed feedback on overall structure and specific content
0.4	24/07/2023	Integration of peer review comments and final editing
0.5	26/07/2023	Revised Figures
1.0	28/07/2023	Document complete and submitted

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the GREAT project consortium under EC grant agreement number 101094766 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	5
List of Tables.....	5
List of Abbreviations.....	6
1. Executive Summary.....	7
2. Introduction.....	7
3. The Underpinning Research Methodological Framework.....	9
3.1 Technologies and Methodology.....	10
4. Conceptual Design.....	11
4.1 Objectives and Research Questions.....	11
4.2 The Research Approach Adopted.....	12
4.2.1 The organisation of the case studies.....	12
4.2.2 The games-based research tools.....	12
4.2.4 The role of stakeholders in determining the inquiry.....	13
4.2.5 Multiple site case studies.....	14
4.2.6 Cumulation of results.....	15
4.3 Research Management.....	15
5. Technical Design.....	16
5.1 Collaborative Study Design.....	16
5.1.1 Citizen Science as an approach.....	16
5.1.2 Intervention Design.....	18
5.2 Data Analysis (Data Interpretation and Outcomes).....	20
5.2.1 Evaluation Methods Tools and Instruments.....	20
5.2.2 DIBL SGI Methodological Approach.....	20
5.2.2 Playmob Methodological Approach.....	21
6. Execution.....	22
6.1 'Sponsoring' of Research.....	22
6.2 Activities with Stakeholders.....	22

6.3 Measurement.....25

 6.3.1 Measurement of the analytical data output of the Games.....25

 6.3.2 Measurement of the activities and case studies26

6.4 Analysis.....26

7. Summary.....28

References30

Annex 131

 The Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (GREAT) Scientific Committee Terms of Reference (ToR)31

List of Figures

Figure 1: The Multi Interdisciplinary Framework (MIR), adapted from Tobi and Kampen (2018).....9

Figure 2: Citizen science involves researchers co-creating with the public in some way during the research process. Illustration by: Lotta W Tomasson/VA CC BY-NC 2.0 ..17

Figure 3: The GREAT Project Research Cycle & Engagement.....18

List of Tables

Table 1: Reliability and validity in case research. Adapted from Yin (1994).27

List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DiBL	Dilemma Based Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Editorial Board
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
MIR	Multi-Interdisciplinary Research
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
TOR	Terms of Reference
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides details of the research methodologies and approaches deployed in the project. The multiple methodologies adopted can facilitate and engage fully with the complex human and technical interactions of the project.

Integral to this is the Citizen Science methodological approach. An approach that permeates research activity undertaken in the project with the aim of democratising the scientific inquiry and outputs. The primary research instrument deployed in GREAT is the Case Study details of the instrument, validation and evaluation methods are provided.

2. Introduction

This deliverable is concerned with the research methodology to be applied to the research, research related activities and outputs undertaken in the Games Realising Effective & Affective Transformation (GREAT) project. The challenge addressed by the project is to gain insight into the cultural role of games in the establishment of a new communication channel between citizens and policy makers centred around transparency and actionable insights. Accordingly, the project involves a series of complex interactions, which requires an equally complex inter/trans multi-disciplinary research methodology, a robust, rigorous methodology able to accommodate a variety of research perspectives to reflect the complex nature of the study.

The research is articulated as a series of case studies. The research intervention is focused on practical activities to harness the cultural and communicative value of games to provide an opportunity for input and feedback to citizens who do not necessarily engage in socio-economic debates and generating new sources of insight for policy stakeholders. The games and interventions we adapt, co-design and implement are not proposed as solutions to the challenge. Rather, they should be considered as research tools that explore the effectiveness of the approach and, generate data, and support a procedure for analysis. Project activities support scalability and adoption from the outset, with case studies which move from testing the concept and applying it in authentic conditions at scale, producing results which are of intrinsic value to the policy stakeholders connected to project partners, and associate partners. The results are built on three assumptions:

1. Games constitute a rich source of data that can reveal a great deal about players' engagement, preferences, and attitudes. However, this is closely

guarded by publishers and developers as a competitive advantage in optimising their games. This data constitutes an opportunity to draw out insights into social preferences and attitudes at scale, this requires new methods of gathering, storing and analysing data, and new forms of engagement with stakeholders, together creating an engagement ecosystem

2. The online interactions of game players generate limited data and learning analytics methods that can be adapted to reveal the connections between game-world interactions and players' engagement with and attitudes towards real world experiences and issues. Games provide an engaging and accessible method for social participation in the political process. Methods developed for Learning Analytics constitute a valuable resource in this analysis and could be integrated into the games to enable the analysis of the interaction data.
3. Policy stakeholders have a need for information on citizens preferences and attitudes, and hence policy stakeholders will be open to and will engage with this input. This engagement is supported by the active participation of policy makers in the project and by the participatory Citizen Science approach adopted that engages stakeholders from the onset. To provide focus, and to facilitate cumulation of results between successive case studies, the project addresses a specific social challenge: the climate crisis. This topic also creates opportunities to demonstrate the transferability of the methods developed, since the case studies will address a diverse range of sub-topics, such as energy costs and consumption, government subsidies for green initiatives, impact on disadvantaged sectors in society, and transport. In year three, the focus will be widened to address a second application in a final 'open' case study. The theme of this case study will be determined from data emanating from preceding cycles and/or be a topical issue of high societal importance. Associate partners will also be invited to establish inquiries into their own local issues.

3. The Underpinning Research Methodological Framework

In this section, we provide detail on the project research method and how this will be applied to all stages and all activities undertaken in the inquiry.

The GREAT project will undertake disciplined inquiry that involves both quantitative and qualitative research methods and these will be framed within an established robust Methodology Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) Framework (Tobi and Kampen 2018). Figure 1 shows how this framework (published under a CC Licence) has been adapted for use in GREAT, and blue text indicates terminology which has been adapted.

Figure 1: The Multi Interdisciplinary Framework (MIR), adapted from Tobi and Kampen (2018).

Grey fill: components inherited from the overall project design

Blue text: terminology which has been adapted (see grant agreement for the original MIR diagram)

Notes:

- (1) The research objectives are determined by the grant agreement.
- (2) The general research questions are derived from the research objectives in this document.
- (3) The specific research questions are determined within each case study in collaboration with stakeholders.
- (4) 'Measurement' comprises quantitative data collection, treatment and exchange. Qualitative data is delivered directly to 'analysis'
- (5) In GREAT, saturation is operationalised as the limits on data collection determined by stakeholders.

Research in the GREAT project involves making sense of a series of highly complex technical and human interactions, this provides the rationale for the selection of this methodology. The aim of the research is to produce substantiated, logical arguments, not reliant on surface plausibility; undertake evidential testing, evaluate, and verify our results. The MIR framework was conceived and designed to support researchers from a variety of disciplinary backgrounds to engage with such complex research questions, and it provides the underlying methodological support for the inquiry.

Even though the MIR framework is well established the nature of engagement in the project required it to be adapted to incorporate participatory research approaches that engage with a variety of stakeholder and citizen groups each with their own, sometime contradictory, expectations and perspectives on the project and more specifically the project direction and outcomes. It is our aim to engage and fully represent these groups as active participants, with agency, in the entire research process. In the project and more specifically in this document, we refer to this participatory research path as Citizen Science.

3.1 Technologies and Methodology

The principal objectives of the project are not to design applied games but to harness games technologies as a digital tool to engage citizens in shaping climate change policy priorities. The project will deploy games primarily as research tools. There are two distinct methods applied in the context of the MIR

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

framework both designed to elicit responses from players and generate qualitative and quantitative data from players.

The Playmob proven approach and methodology, which is elaborated upon in this document, could be described as a playful approach to engaging players of digital games on mobile devices. Within the context of the MIR framework the approach is characterised as a sophisticated research instrument designed to generate data from the interactions and responses of players to questions relating to priorities in climate change policy. The instrument is designed generate significant volumes of quantitative data that will be analysed and visualised (using analytic tools such as MS Power Business Intelligence) for further analysis by the project team.

The SGI use dilemma games approach as an instrument is designed to gather both quantitative and deeper qualitative data observing the behaviours and interactions of players to designed (with stakeholders) dilemmas.

4. Conceptual Design

In this section, we provide detail of the research conceptual design of the project including detail the core research objectives and research questions to be addressed by the project.

4.1 Objectives and Research Questions

This section reproduces the objectives of the GREAT project, which are set out in the Grant Agreement, Project: 101094766. The Grant Agreement does not specify the research questions, which will guide the research that will enable the project to reach these objectives. That is undertaken here, following reflection on the test activities of Cycle 1 of project activities. Research questions are formulated for each of the four principal objectives of the project shown below in italics.

1. *To establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policymakers.*
2. *To understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.*
3. *To provide practical guidance for games developers and policy stakeholders.*

4. *To assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges.*

4.2 The Research Approach Adopted

4.2.1 The organisation of the case studies

At the centre of the approach adopted to provide answers to these questions is a series of case studies which runs throughout the project. These are organised as follows. The project is organised in five cycles. The first is a test cycle, refining the method, each subsequent cycle contains one or more case studies. Each of the five cycles of project activity involves one or more case studies.

Each cycle has four stages

- Cycle phase 1: intervention design.
- Cycle phase 2: preparation of case studies,
- Cycle phase 3: data gathering and analysis
- Cycle phase 4: conclusions and insight.

The phases are carried out within case studies in parallel in the cycle, although not necessarily synchronously.

The workplan articulates the phases into stages, corresponding to tasks within work packages in the project plan this will be dealt with in Deliverable D4.2 (M12) Case/Pilot Study Design.

4.2.2 The games-based research tools

The case studies will make use of two games-based research tools.

Short interactions at a large scale: A short interaction involves a time limited interaction to a maximum of 3-7 minutes embedded within a larger gaming experience Partner Playmob has a platform with the capacity to embed quiz type games designed by the GREAT project within existing leisure based digital games in any region of the world. Basic and anonymous demographic data is gathered as part of the quiz. The population can be restricted both in terms of the target game, and also the geographic area, down to the level of a postcode. The quiz format appeals to a broad range of gamers, and the popularity and familiarity of the format has been seen to secure high participation. Budget has been allocated for the cost of delivering the quizzes to a population of hundreds of thousands of thousands. Question design and development will be carried out collaboratively with stakeholders, supported by

a team of experts from Playmob. The Playmob platform is a powerful tool for obtaining large scale responses shedding light on a specific issue.

Long interactions at a small scale: A long interaction is a full game playing experience of usually more than a couple of hours duration Partner SGI provides a dilemma-based game platform, which generates and orchestrates serious games for use by stakeholders. The DiBL (Dilemma Based Learning) platform supports creation of scenarios involve close interaction with participating players, usually guided by a facilitator. The players are split into teams with different roles in the games. As the scenario evolves, new insight emerges and players agree on how to progress raising consequences for how the game evolves. The games can be carried out face-to-face or online. The DiBL platform is a powerful tool for in depth exploration of differing perspectives and opinions held by stakeholders.

Key aspects of the development of the GREAT method will be to

- investigate different ways in which stakeholders (including citizens) can collaborate in designing interventions with these two tools, and interpreting the results.
- Establish the benefits of different ways of combining these two tools, with results flowing between the two systems in a variety of ways.

4.2.3 Additional Research Tools Deployed in the Project

The project will deploy several research tools situated within the MIR framework. These tools will include:

- Research Questionnaires (to capture both qualitative and quantitative data incorporating a combination of Open and Closed questions and Likert scale responses.
- Interviews (including the preparation of supporting guidelines)
- Citizen Science Workshops with stakeholders.
- Design Workshops with partners.

4.2.4 The role of stakeholders in determining the inquiry

Each case study is distinguished by addressing a topic-specific research question related to the climate crisis, or to whichever topic is the vehicle for the case study. This question is established in collaboration with stakeholders, and carries through the case study to the final production of an insight report. In

this sense, in each case study the GREAT project may be considered to be 'commissioned' by a stakeholder group to carry out activities to facilitate and support the stakeholder's inquiry into citizens opinions and attitudes. For the project, however, the research consists of an inquiry into how best this facilitation and support can be carried out using games-based activities.

4.2.5 Multiple site case studies

The GREAT project adopts a multiple-case study approach, the individual case studies contributing to an understanding of the projects research objectives. Yin (2018) provides valuable guidance on how such a research undertaking should be carried out, which is worth reproducing in full.

Selecting the multiple cases also raises a new set of questions. Here, a major insight is to consider multiple-case studies as one would consider multiple experiments—that is, to follow a "replication" design. This is far different from the misleading analogy that incorrectly considers the multiple cases to be similar to the multiple respondents in a survey (or to the multiple subjects within an experiment)—that is, to follow a "sampling" design. The methodological differences between these two views are revealed by the different rationales underlying the replication as opposed to sampling designs. Replication, not sampling logic, for multiple-case studies. The replication logic is directly analogous to that used in multiple experiments (see Barlow, Nock, & Hersen, 2008). For example, upon uncovering a significant finding from a single experiment, an ensuing and pressing priority would be to replicate this finding by conducting a second, third, and even more experiments. Some of the replications might attempt to duplicate the exact conditions of the original experiment. Other replications might alter one or two experimental conditions considered challenges to the original finding, to see whether the finding can still be duplicated. With both kinds of replications, the original finding would be strengthened. The design of multiple-case studies follows an analogous logic. Each case must be carefully selected so that the individual case studies either (a) predict similar results (a literal replication) or (b) predict contrasting results but for anticipatable reasons (a theoretical replication). The ability to conduct 6 or 10 individual case studies, arranged effectively within a multiple-case design, is analogous to the ability to conduct 6 to 10 experiments on related topics: A few case studies (2 or 3) might aim at being literal replications, whereas a few other case studies (4 to 6) might be designed to pursue two different patterns of theoretical replications. (Yin, 2018, p.90-99).

This is the approach that is adopted by the GREAT project, with the proviso that 'literal replication' will be difficult or impossible to achieve, given the changing circumstances and availability of participants even in the same location, while conditions in different locations are likely to be still more contrasting. Thus the

question arises of how cumulation can be achieved between the different case studies, when the conditions which condition the results are significantly divergent.

4.2.6 Cumulation of results

In responding to the methodological challenge of cumulation, the GREAT project builds on the work of Pawson and Tilley in 'realistic evaluation'. This approach enables the project to propose models of "what works for whom in what circumstances" (Pawson, 2013, p.15), formulated in terms of Context, Intervention, causal Mechanism and Outcome (i.e. CIMO configurations). The different sites of the case studies provide data to identify how games-based activities influence factors and contexts and which lead to differing patterns of stakeholder involvement, behaviour and activities. The methodological challenge is to draw generalisable conclusions from this varied mass of data, which can be successfully applied in other contexts. By modelling research outcomes as CIMOs a number of benefits are achieved. Firstly, project outcomes are able to reflect the complexity of the social and technical landscape that is being studied, rather than treating the variation in context as a confounding factor which should be eliminated from the discussion. Secondly, the CIMO configurations enable clear predictions to be made, of the type "If you adopt this approach in this educational context, then these results may be expected". Such predictions provide a clear starting point for validation and possible adjustment in contexts which have not been included in the present research, and so support the cumulation of results across programmes of European and national research. Thirdly, the results will facilitate the project's task of developing context sensitive recommendations for facilitating citizen's engagement with policy stakeholders at all levels.

4.3 Research Management

The project research management will be coordinated within Work Package 4 (WP4) but will report directly to the Project Board and an appointed Scientific Committee established with Terms of Reference (TOR), which are appended to this deliverable in Annex 1.

The purpose of the committee is to provide support and guidance of the project for all scientific activities undertaken in the project. The Scientific Committee was established on the 01/03/2023 and will run for the duration of the project in 31/03/2026. The committee is chaired by a 'critical friend' & senior academic

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

representative from one of the partners not leading this work package (WP4) this is currently Professor David Griffiths from consortium partner UNIR. This separation of WP4 leadership from chairing of the Scientific Committee ensures academic independence and scrutiny of research activities. These include all academic outputs and dissemination activities of the project team including journal articles, books, conference papers and to provide input and support to Work Package 6 (WP6) responsible for Engagement, Dissemination, and Sustainability. In this context the Scientific committee is also responsible for the custodianship of the Project Publication Plan which provides details to project partners of the approach and management of the scientific publication activities and outputs of the project.

5. Technical Design

In this section, we present the overarching technical design, together with the underpinning theoretical approach to the collaborative study design.

5.1 Collaborative Study Design

The project will adopt collaborative approaches to the design of the study and of the project interventions. The project team is multi-disciplinary, incorporating social scientists and computer scientists from a variety of scientific, technological, arts and humanities backgrounds. The project will adopt citizen Science approaches situated within the MIR framework.

5.1.1 Citizen Science as an approach

Citizen Science has emerged as a powerful and innovative approach to scientific research, enabling collaboration between scientists and the wider population and public in the pursuit of knowledge and understanding. Whilst citizen science practice has a long history, it is only in recent decades that it has gained recognition for its potential to provide robust outcomes of scientific inquiry with societal dialogue.

Citizen Science represents a paradigmatic shift from more established, traditional top-down research models to that of a more inclusive and participatory approach, an approach where citizens are empowered to actively contribute to scientific investigations. The process enables the creation of trust and has contributed to efforts to democratize science.

Whilst there is no single established definition, most scholars do agree that it refers to the active participation of citizens in research activities. 'The Characteristics of Citizen Science' (Haklay et al. 2020) provides a succinct overview of that which Citizen Science embraces and where the demarcation

lines which distinguish it from alternative research practices. Figure 2 gives an overview of the mechanisms for public engagement within any phase of the research process.

CITIZEN SCIENCE = co-creation with the public during the research process

Figure 2: Citizen science involves researchers co-creating with the public in some way during the research process. Illustration by: Lotta W Tomasson/VA CC BY-NC 2.0

One of the fundamental principles of citizen science is the democratization of knowledge production (Irwin, 1995). It recognizes that scientific research should not be the exclusive domain of experts and professionals but should be accessible and open to all members of society. By actively involving citizens in research projects, citizen science can break down traditional barriers that may exist between researchers and the public, fostering a sense of ownership, empowerment, and engagement among participants.

This approach serves to enhance scientific literacy and public understanding of science and can nurture a sense of shared responsibility and collective action towards addressing pressing societal and environmental challenges. Thus, we find it very appropriate to apply Citizen Science methods in the GREAT project.

Co-funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

By involving citizens and specific stakeholders as active contributors in the different phases of our research cycle we gain diverse perspectives, from the identification of the local issues related to the climate crisis to the contextualized data interpretation applied to the data collected during our game interventions.

Figure 3: The GREAT Project Research Cycle & Engagement

Figure 3, above, indicates the planned engagement cycle that we have developed for our Citizen Science approach in the GREAT project. The figure illustrates how our citizens and specific stakeholders will be actively engaged in various phases of the GREAT research cycle.

It is recognised that research cycles may require bespoke approaches within the project methodological framework to accurately reflect the scale, scope and individual requirements of each of the stakeholder groupings. Consequently, the iterative nature of the research plan coupled with the exploratory nature presents challenges in undertaking reproducible research within the project.

5.1.2 Intervention Design

Co-funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

The intervention design involves the use of several bespoke research instruments, that reflect both the interdisciplinary nature of the study and the incorporation of citizen science approaches across the research activities. This circular approach is represented in Figure 4 below and elaborated in the following text. Our principal research instruments are the applied games themselves characterised in two distinct methodological approaches.

5.1.2.1 Create and Prioritise Research Topics

The instrument deployed in the project to create and prioritise the research project adopt a citizen science approach. This involves the establishment of several workshops, or as they are referred to in the project cycles.

Over the term of the research project, we will convene a series of these cycles (a minimum number of five cycles will occur with various representative groups of stakeholders and citizens). The intervention design is dealt with fully within the accompanying Work Package 2 (WP2) of the project 'Intervention Design' and detailed in yearly reports for the duration of the project in deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3. These cycles will allow the project to articulate the contextual priorities identified within each of the cycles. The first of which took place in Frankfurt over the course of a few months in 2023.

5.1.2.2 Understand Themes and Dilemmas

The themes generated within the cycle activity inform the design of the research intervention. Initially these will be examined within the Dilemma Based Learning Approach (DiBL) of the project. The translation of Dilemmas into functional applied games is undertaken by SGI to develop the instrument by which the project can gather both quantitative and qualitative data. The qualitative data is then analysed to inform the design of further quantitative tools to be embedded within existing games using the Playmob tested methodology. The design of the Games instruments is dealt with in Work Package 3 (WP3) of the Project 'Technical Development and Re-Purposing of Games'.

5.1.2.3 Collaborate in Study Design.

Adopting the Citizen Science approach allows us to engage with our stakeholders at all stages of the research process and allows for an iterative approach to the design of the study and interventions reflecting the diverse nature of the study group.

5.1.2.4 Run Pilot Games and Gather Data

Quiz type games embedded within existing leisure based digital games. The Playmob Platform will be deployed to engage gamers internationally throughout the project on the topic of the climate crisis. A Reskinable Mini-Game: This is the engagement tool which will be deployed to engage, gather anonymous insights and learn more about the player. Using a proprietary quiz engine and drawing on pre-existing datasets, themes such as transport, energy, farms and food, nature, protecting people and the green economy will be tackled. The quiz format also appeals to a broad range of gamers, and the popularity and familiarity of the selected engagement format will secure high participation. Question design and development supported by a team of experts.

Dilemma based games designed to explore the scenarios (initially developed within the cycle workshops). The SGI Approach of Dilemma Based Learning (DiBL). The DiBL platform supports creation of a scenario that a facilitator guides but based on close interaction with participating players. The players are split into teams with different roles in the games. As the scenario evolves new insight emerges and players agree on how to progress raising consequences for how the game evolves.

5.2 Data Analysis (Data Interpretation and Outcomes)

The approach to data analysis will combine appropriate methodological instruments for analysis and evaluation of the large volumes of quantitative and qualitative data generated throughout activities during the course of the project.

5.2.1 Evaluation Methods Tools and Instruments

Whilst there is a significant overlap, evaluation of the project processes, methods and data will be undertaken in the complimentary work package of this project Work Package 5 (WP5) and will be specifically dealt with in Deliverable D5.1.

5.2.2 DIBL SGI Methodological Approach

The DIBL methodology involves deploying mediated and supported dilemma-based games with stakeholder groups. Data is produced and inferences drawn from the choices players make when facing dilemmas in gameplay such as should I turn right or should I turn left? What are the consequences of those choices? What does a choice indicate in the context of the study?

The findings of the DIBL activities may be used, together with other data sources, to inform the design of large scale Playmob process as detailed below.

5.2.2 Playmob Methodological Approach

The Playmob methodology has been applied extensively in commercial application to address specific complex questions.

Figure 4: The Playmob methodology

In essence the method involves running pilot games and gathering large volumes of data from which inferences can be drawn through both machine and human data interpretation. This allows us to assess the project and process on an ongoing basis.

5.2.3 Data and Learning Analytics

It should be noted that additional instruments will be deployed within our methodological approach. Most significantly sophisticated data analytical approaches will be undertaken detail of which is provided in the accompanying GREAT project Work Package 3 with associated tasks and deliverables.

6. Execution

In this section, we provide detail of how the research plan will be executed. This involves details of the activities we will undertake with various stakeholder groups. How we aim to measure the findings of the research intervention and our method(s) for analysing the data produced.

6.1 'Sponsoring' of Research

It is recognised in the project that the partner effectively selected to sponsoring the research should have an objective. Given the partner organisations will be drawn from government and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO) each will have an objective in 'sponsoring' the activity. This may be to test an assumption over a policy action at a local (micro) level for example 'We should convert this brown field site to green field for environmental reasons' or at the macro level "If we reduce carbon emissions in Europe it will help us address global climate change issues". The approach is flexible to deal with a variety of scenarios at the Macro and Micro level.

It is also recognised by the project that the sponsor of the case study research activity should have a fundamental question or problem to be addressed. This will ensure partner organisations are motivated to engage positively with the activity. These questions and problems can be refined and well defined through a process of consensus in the cycle stage of development as detailed in this document. It is essential that partners are engaged over the full course of the cycle to ensure iterative development of the problem space can occur.

6.2 Activities with Stakeholders

Cycle phase 1: intervention design. The policy theme and the research questions for the case study are defined in a collaborative process with stakeholders. The games and interventions are then designed in a three-stage process, with policy stakeholders and citizens involved in collaborative design throughout, in workshops, focus groups and interviews.

Stage one develops design challenges and use cases, answering the question "What will this game achieve and how". It will identify authentic dilemmas which concern them and the kinds of information which they would find valuable, and the user groups who can provide this information. Data from game play, and activities with stakeholders will identify needs for insight, to meet the nuanced

needs of our target audience. Publicly available information on the climate crisis and other social issues will be collected and analysed to provide insight into the dilemmas selected by the project. This will help ensure optimal levels of user engagement, satisfy the needs of audiences and identify opportunities for future iterations. The output of this stage is a design hypothesis, which specifies the expected engagement of users, the usable information which will be generated, and the value that this information will have to policy stakeholders.

Stage two develops design briefs, answering the question “What game characteristics are required to meet this design challenge”. It will provide detail on the specific issues and challenges raised by a dilemma, identifying or authoring appropriate thematic content, and specifying sources of data, analysis and outputs.

Stage three develops wireframes, answering the question “How can this design brief be implemented”, providing a specification which can be passed to WP3 for technical development.

Cycle phase 2: preparation of case studies. The intervention theme and research questions, and the games activities are provided to WP4 and the schedule of case study activities defined. In parallel the wireframes produced in phase one will be passed on to WP3, responsible for implementation. Although the main purpose of the GREAT project is not the creation of games, nevertheless the project will produce a number of new games in rapid development cycles. This is feasible because the consortium includes two commercial games providers whose development systems enable us to reskin, or develop on top of, existing technology for use throughout the duration of the project. PM specialises in short mobile games which can be delivered to large numbers of individual players, while SGI focuses on collaborative games, with smaller groups of users making a greater commitment of time to the game.

Other partners will contribute effort in the development of games on these platforms. Partner DIPF will contribute its expertise in data analytics, UNIR its strong track record in the production of educational games, and UoB will provide expertise from its Centre for Games Development. A development group will be set up including all these partners, which will manage the agile development process. The platforms will be configured, adapted, and where necessary extended to meet the requirements set out in the wireframes. A toolkit of open-source tools will be selected and deployed to support analysis and the creation of representations of the result of that analysis. This toolkit will be configured, and algorithms implemented which support the data analysis specified in the

collaborative design process. WP3 will also be responsible for deploying the games which have been created and maintaining their delivery for pilots.

Cycle phase 3: data gathering and analysis. This phase is carried out in this work package. Activities will range widely from small scale activities to large numbers of users, gathering both quantitative data from the games, and qualitative data from interviews and focus groups. The case studies will seek to answer the research questions and test the design hypotheses developed in phase one. They will involve the whole information flow of game play, data gathering, analysis and engagement with policy stakeholders, evaluating the transferable methods developed by the project. The case studies will also provide feedback on the effectiveness of game designs and the dynamics of communication patterns with user groups. In all cases, the respondents in GREAT research will be volunteers who have given their informed consent to participation. Three different strategies will be used to identify participants in trials:

- First, trials and case studies will be addressed to the general public, both through social media, and through the purchase by the project of commercial placement of ads in hit mobile games where people spend long periods of time. The project aims to reach a substantial number of players through this recruitment method. Players opt in to get involved with topics which matter to them, and the game appears as a 'playable advert' through in-game media targeting specific locations and audiences. The project will target six markets in Europe, to reach a realistic sample of diverse audiences.
- Second, users for trials will be identified from within the partner organisation and the associate partners, and particularly from among the students and lecturers of the academic partners.
- Third, groups of interested parties will be identified for participation in case studies, including in playing collaborative games. This third group will make extensive use of the policy stakeholder networks of partners (especially PM, FU and UNIR), and of associate partners.

In line with the citizen science approach of the project, participants will be invited to participate in analysis of the results and their implications. On completion of phase three a large amount of anonymous, aggregate data will have been amassed, providing a rich corpus for the application of data analytics, as well as reflection with focus groups. Data generated by the games will be

analysed to provide insight into the preferences and attitudes of citizens, in a process informed by collaborative design with citizens and policy stakeholders.

A great deal of data is generated while playing game, and this will be gathered and analysed. The data will be managed in line with the project Data Management Plan. The project will explore the use of instruments for evaluating the game. Project Partner DIPF is developing a Large Language Model (LLM) instance that could potentially provide a secure solution to exploring LLM's within the GREAT project.

The relevant data includes players' progress towards a goal, changes in the rate of change of this progress, the timing and content of their input, and (in social games) their choice of interlocutors and their interactions can be gathered during gameplay and analysed. The detailed timing of players activities can also be revealing of their engagement with an issue, and their degree of certainty, including the time spent viewing information (by a single or team player), time reading questions/instructions, completion rates in single or multiplayer games, talking to other players in a multiplayer game as well as forum traces, number of correct and incorrect answers, and time taken to complete a level or challenge. A/B testing will also be used to focus in on specific variables. All of this information will provide insight into players' attitudes and preferences and can feed into reports on citizen's views and engagement with policy issues, as well as informing the development of public information strategies. As far as possible, the emerging data is exposed to the project team, and to stakeholders as a resource for their reflection and comment.

Cycle phase 4: conclusions and insight. In this phase the conclusions of the case study are formulated. These include the preparation of scientific outputs for publication, feedback for the design of instruments, processes and participant engagement. In collaboration with stakeholders, the insight from the cycle is drawn out, insight briefings prepared for policy stakeholders, and their feedback elicited. The GREAT method is reviewed and updated. Phase 4 is carried out in collaboration with stakeholders and constitutes a preparatory stage for the next iteration of the cycle. Engagement and targeting strategies are reviewed and optimised after each cycle.

6.3 Measurement

6.3.1 Measurement of the analytical data output of the Games

The project will deploy a variety of approaches to analyse and measure the data and impact of the interventions using both human and automated established

analytical methods, instruments and tools of quantitative and qualitative analysis.

6.3.2 Measurement of the activities and case studies

The case study as a research method in social science is well-established. Case studies can be descriptive, test theory and additionally provide theory as theory-building. Case study research cannot be categorised as sampling research. The purpose of the case study research is to get an in-depth understanding of the complexity of the object of study. In the GREAT case studies, we will aim to balance and capture the complexity of interactions to produce rich content for further analysis.

In the GREAT project games will be deployed adopting an innovative dual data generation strategy for games combined with more traditional research methods. This is achieved through commercial placement of short interaction mobile games in popular hit titles at mass market scale. The benefit of this approach is to provide a large flow of data which is responsive to live social issues and developments, and representative of target populations. We recognise that short format games have corresponding limits in generating in-depth responses to complex knowledge domains and poorly defined problems such as the climate change crisis. In parallel the project will work with longer format dilemma games that support reflection and discussion, and data from both types of game will be integrated in answering our case study research questions.

6.4 Analysis

The project will undertake analysis of the individual case studies. The case studies will be designed to capture the complexity of interactions between stakeholders and the technology applied. Case studies are widely used as a methodology in management and specifically operations management and are extremely useful in developing new theory and this was the predominant factor in choosing the methodology in the GREAT Project.

The method is particularly suitable for use in technology interventions in identifying the dynamics of technology implementation that transcend the technology being used to illuminate decisions or sets of decisions. (Yin 1994) describes case studies as:

"An empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident and the investigator has little control over events" (Yin. 1994 & 2014).

Test	GREAT Case Study Tactic	Phase in Which Tactic Occurs	GREAT WP
Construct Validity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use Multiple Sources of Evidence 2. Establish Chain of Evidence 3. Have the Key Contributors Review the Case Study Report 	Data Collection Data Collection Composition	WP2, WP4 & WP5
Internal Validity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Do Pattern Matching or Explanation Building or Time Series Analysis 	Data Analysis	WP4 & WP5
External Validity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Use Replication Logic in Multiple Case Studies 	Research Design	WP2, WP3 & WP4
Reliability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Use Study Protocol 7. Develop Case Study Database 	Data Collection Data Collection	WP3 & WP4

Table 1: Reliability and validity in case research. Adapted from Yin (1994).

Whilst there is no defined analytical strategy, the project will follow general principals to ensure to ensure reliability and validity as detailed in Figure 6 below and the analytical techniques described as by Yin (2014, pp. 136-142)

- The project will rely on our theoretical propositions.
- The project will work our data from its baseline.
- The project will develop a detailed case description.
- We will examine all plausible rival explanations.

We will further explore case study analytical techniques including pattern identification and matching, explanation building, time series analysis, logic models and will undertake cross case synthesis evaluation.

We recognise the challenge in developing causal theories in the absence of or inability to develop common rules and methods for distinguishing phenomenon from the context of the intervention. We will attempt to ensure that the case studies adopt consistent definitions to address concerns of cumulation between the various case studies.

Yazan (2015) and Merriam (1998) represents six strategies to enhance internal validity and these will be adopted by the project. These are triangulation, stakeholder/partner checks, long-term observation, peer examination, participatory research (the project is strong in this perspective) and disclosure of researcher bias).

They recommend three techniques to ensure internal validity (explanation of investigator's position regarding the study, triangulation, and use of an audit trail) and three techniques to enhance external validity (use of thick description, typicality or modal categories, and multisite designs).

Case studies are one of the dominant methodologies applied to considering technical interventions.

7. Summary

This deliverable provides a review of the research frameworks and instruments and methods that are relevant to the GREAT project.

The project is extremely and inherently complex. Consequently, the GREAT approach requires a series of equally complex models and methods that are effective in dealing with multiple and divergent activities, multiple data sources, data sets with multiple stakeholders with different needs. To provide coherence.

The MIR framework provides the overarching methodological approach to the GREAT project from an Operational perspective this provides us with three distinct phases of the project **Conceptual, Technical, Execution** and **Integration**.

Conceptual (relates to WP's 2,3,4 and 5)

This deals with the **research objectives** and **research questions** to be addressed in the project. These will be reviewed on an ongoing basis.

Technical (relates to WP's 2,3,4)

The Study design instruments and Data analysis involves deploying the digital games tools these are informed through the cycles and various workshops who

deploy citizen science approaches. The games data (Qualitative and Quantitative) underpins the case studies produced. The Case Studies (and data. Presented) are analysed using established case study methodologies as detailed in this document. Methodology as informed by Figure 1 of this document.

Execution (relates to WP's 3,4,5)

This includes a series of cycles with various stakeholders. A cycle includes a citizen science-based workshop to develop key questions to inform the Games interventions. Methodology as informed by Figure 1 of this document.

Integration (relates to 4,5 and informs 2 and 3)

This is where a synthesis of the GREAT project Case Studies is undertaken which in turn feeds back into future Cycles and Case Study Designs as the project progresses. Methodology as informed by Figure 1 of this document.

References

- Barlow, D. H., Nock, M., & Hersen, M. (2008). Single case research designs: Strategies for studying behaviour change.
- Ebneyamini.S Reza.M & Moghadam.S (2018) Toward Developing a Framework for Conducting Case Study Research International Journal of Qualitative Methods Volume 17: 1–11
- Haklay.M, Motion. A. Balázs. B, Kieslinger, B, Greshake. T, Bastian, Nold. C, Dörler. D, Fraisl. D, Riemenschneider.D, Heigl.F, Brounéus.F, Hager.G, Heuer. K, Wagenknecht. K, Vohland.k , Shanley. L, Deveaux. L, Ceccaroni.L, Weißpflug. M, When.U. (2020). ECSA's Characteristics of Citizen Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758668> (Accessed July 2023)
- Irwin, A. (1995). Citizen Science: A Study of People, Expertise, and Sustainable Development. London: Routledge.
- Merriam, S. B. (1998). Qualitative Research and Case Study Applications in Education. Revised and Expanded from "Case Study Research in Education": ERIC.
- Pawson, R. (2013). The Science of Evaluation: A Realist Manifesto. Sage.
- Tobi, H., Kampen, J.K. Research design: the methodology for interdisciplinary research framework. *Qual Quant* 52, 1209–1225 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-017-0513-8>
- Yazan, B. (2015). Three approaches to case study methods in education: In Yin, Merriam, and Stake. *The Qualitative Report*, 20, 134–152.
- Yin, R. K. (1994). Case study research: Design & methods. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Yin, R. K. (2014), Case Study Research: Design and methods. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

Annex 1

The Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (GREAT) Scientific Committee Terms of Reference (ToR)

Role/Purpose The role of GREAT Scientific Committee will provide strategic direction and leadership to ensure that all academic outputs of the GREAT project maintain consistent academic quality standards in respect of ethics, integrity and rigour and ensure that all outputs fully comply with the requirements as detailed in the GREAT project (101094766) grant agreement. The Committee will encourage the creation of academic outputs.

Term This Terms of Reference is effective from March 1st, 2023, and continues until March 1st, 2026, the expected date of completion of the GREAT project and terminated by agreement between the parties.

Membership The GREAT Scientific Committee will comprise:

One Representative from all Partners and Two from Associate Partner UoB (as Leaders of WP4). Professor Hendrik Drachsler Project Coordinator DIPF 0000-0001-8407- 5314 Dr Celestine Iwendi Associate Partner UoB 0000-0003-4350- 3911 Professor Paul Hollins Associate Partner UoB 0000-0003-1739- 9882 Professor Dai Griffiths Partner UNIR 0000-0002-6863- 2456 Jude Ower Associate Partner PM (Optional) 0000-0002-7676- 1792 Simon Engfeldt Nielsen Partner SGI (Optional) 0000-0002-4286- 1111 Katharina Koller Partner ZSI 0000-0002-6405-3297 Professor Aravella Zachariou Partner FU 0000-0002-0721- 7603

Roles and Responsibilities:

The Scientific Committee is accountable for:

- Fostering collaboration
- Removing obstacles to the GREAT project successful delivery of academic outputs.
- Maintaining at all times the focus of the project on the agreed scope and academic outputs and outcomes.
- Ensuring Compliance with all requirements for the academic outputs as defined in the GREAT project agreement.

The membership of the advisory group will commit to:

- Attending all scheduled Scientific Committee meetings. (Exception of 'Optional' attendees.
- Championing the project academic outputs in all areas of personal influence.
- Sharing all communications and information produced by the Committee across all GREAT project partners and Associates partners.
- Making timely decisions and taking prompt action so as to not hold up the project.
- Notifying members of the Scientific Committee, as soon as practical, if any matter arises which may be deemed to affect the academic outputs project.
- Attending all meetings and if necessary, nominate a proxy.

Members of the Scientific Committee will expect:

- That each member will be provided with complete, accurate and meaningful information in a timely manner.
- To be given reasonable time to make key decisions.
- To be alerted to potential risks and issues that could impact the project, as they arise.
- Open and honest discussions, without resort to any misleading assertions.
- Ongoing 'health checks' to verify the overall status and 'health' of the Committee.

Meetings

- All meetings will be chaired by (To Be Nominated)
- A meeting quorum will be Four members of the Scientific Committee.
- Decisions made by consensus (i.e. members are satisfied with the decision even though it may not be their first choice). If not possible, the Scientific Committee chair will make the final decision. Meeting agendas minutes will be provided by Dr Celestine Iwendi , this includes:
 - Preparing agendas and providing any supporting papers.
 - Preparing meeting notes and information.
- All Meetings will be held virtually as agreed for (specify time to be agreed) . If required subgroup meetings will be arranged outside of these times at a time convenient to subgroup members. Amendment, Modification or Variation This Terms of Reference may be amended, varied or modified in writing after consultation and agreement by the Scientific Committee.

